

Vol:1, Issue: 3 pp:342-345

JEL Codes: L8, L82, L89

ALSHARARI T.F. (2020). "Influence of Social Media, Facebook, on Language
vol: 1 issue: 3 pp: 342-345

Keywords: social media, facebook, language .

Article Type Review Article

Influence of Social Media, Facebook, on Language

Arrived Date
28.05.2020

Accepted Date
29.07.2020

Published Date
31.07.2020

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ABSTRACT

Rapid development of internet technology; has reshaped the communication area. With the new media products consisting of the combination of the internet and computer systems, the phenomenon of interaction gained strength, so social networks became popular. In this study, the effect of social media on the language is discussed in the context of the literature.

INTRODUCTION

The emergence of the internet has significantly transformed our daily use of language as a form of communication (Ferreiro, 2010). The internet has brought about a linguistic revolution that particularly affects the written language which has resulted in online language that varies from traditional language and media. Various formulas have been created that have led to more expressiveness to the traditional formal written mode, word or expression that can lead to global popularity online in a very short time (Ferreiro, 2010). All of these new modifications have brought about new kinds of online language known as e-dialect, e-sociolects, e-slang, e-conversation, e-literacy, etc. Hence the internet and in particular the social media like Facebook has had a huge effect on the chosen vocabulary of language which is greatly affected by technological advancements like social media.

The emergence of the internet had affected language and continues to impact on language in fast and various ways. The influences of the internet and by proxy, Facebook, and other social media, have had on the way we speak or write has been greatly criticized and blamed for affecting literacy, especially on younger generations (Bembe, 2008). Several famous figures have made pronouncements of their opinion on the consequences of this change of language as a result of the technological revolution. In effect, the opinions clearly state that the impact of the revolution is no different than destroying language, pillaging the punctuation, saving sentences, and raping the vocabulary (Ferreiro, 2010).

To discuss the influence of social media or the internet on language is not without discussing demographics. Demographics are important for the determination of the language use of a social media platform which developed over a period. Literature has shown that there is a "seismic generational gap" in connection to how language is used on the internet and particularly in social media (Sabater, 2015; Ferreiro, 2010).

The generational gap has been described as the situation in which the old and young people fail to understand each other due to the respective levels of experience, opinions, habits, and behavior, which

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is the case in the application or use of language (Ferreiro, 2010).

1.0 Effect of the advent of the Internet

The coming of the internet has left an indelible mark of transforming people's lives. Hence this has also affected the language they use (Blattner & Fiori, 2009; Ferreiro, 2010). This change has become evident over the last several decades due to the speed with which this development of technology has occurred (Severin & Tankard, 1997). The use of language has become adapted to a kind of environment where the written format is used but on the other hand, a more informal style is also being commonly used. These informal ones are known as e-dialect, e-sociolects, e-slang, e-conversation, e-literacy, etc. (Androutsopoulos & Ziegler, 2004; Ferreiro, 2010). Language may be different because of the online context of the speaker such as the kind of technological device being used. Moreover, speaking language is different and used in the different way as in the use of computer or a smartphone as mobile phone keyboards use requires different mode of use with specific letters. The advent of the internet brought about the emergence of other less popular terms such as cyber-slang, chatspeak or digitalese (Ferreiro, 2010).

The coming about of the new conventions of language is not unique to the internet as broadcasting and printing equally have created new ones. However, internet users use these conventions of language with much care. This is particularly the case these expressions had gone through some change over time such as in the case of *LOL* ('*Laughing Out Loud*'), which now has a completely different meaning from the original. Now, this may mean sarcasm or passive-aggressiveness (Ferreiro, 2010).

3.0 Factors of change of language

Several factors contribute to how people speak. Some of these factors are age, level of education, or origin which all contribute to linguistic change and have been demonstrated by research in sociolinguistics (Ferreiro, 2010). The effect of change occurs over time and therefore the change or influence of the social media on the language will also occur over time and this will make the difference between those with access to the internet, or belong to a particular social class in a specific environment, and those who are not. At the forefront of these changes in is language used by the young generations, especially females (Ferreiro, 2010). This is because of the fragmentation of the population that the internet mostly affects because females are the most frequently users of social media. This is particularly evident with words or slang from the drag community that is now a fixed expression in the social media which are steadily creeping into everyday speech (Alsulami, 2016; Ferreiro, 2010).

4.0 Language Vocabulary Changes

Vocabulary remains a key part of the language that is greatly susceptible to change. With the great impact of the internet, the impact on language has been significant. Moreover, this impact has been and continues to affect vocabulary. Social media is a medium through which people come to contact and influence one and another and as a consequence affect language as well (Paolillo, 2001; Ferreiro, 2010). During the last several decades, there has been a rise in the addition of new terms and updating of dictionaries to stay ahead of technological advancements of slang terms that originate from the Net, because a word can quickly become globally trendy in a matter of days. Facebook for example has contributed to the emergence of slang and lingo etc. Facebook is one of the first platforms to gain popularity right from its beginning. Facebook has introduced new meanings to *wall*, *friend*, and *like* to mention a few. *Wall* is referred to different from the conventional dictionary meaning but in the context of Facebook implies a part of a Facebook 'user's profile where users can post status updates and receive messages from friends' (Ferreiro, 2010). *Friend*, similarly implies in Facebook context a contact on a 'social media networking website' which is different from its common meaning. These is also slang. Slang is the term for a very informal language that is usually spoken rather than written. Slang is a common language of a particular group. The use of slang may also be used to connect people with others who share an idea or interest and is only understood by the group members.

5.0 Self-Presentation in Managing Relationships on Facebook

The merging of audiences in social media and the variety of participation structures they present, including different audience sizes and interaction targets, pose questions about how people respond to these new communication situations. Self-presentational and relational concerns can be seen through the analysis of language styles on Facebook based on status updates, wall posts, and private messages. These messages varied in certain characteristics of language style, revealing differences in underlying self-presentational and relational concerns based on the publicness and directedness of the interaction. Positive emotion words correlated with self-reported self-presentational concerns in status updates, suggesting a strategic use of sharing positive emotions in public and no directed communication via status updates (Bazarova et al., 2012). Verbal immediacy correlated with partner familiarity in wall posts but not in private messages, suggesting that verbal immediacy cues serve as markers to differentiate between more and less familiar partners in public wall posts.

6.0 Gender Differences in Seeking Support through Facebook

Social support is important in social network ties and social commerce because supportive interactions make social network members closer to one another and more comfortable with exchanging information. When people have problems or need advice, their friends with strong tie offer more help and have more power to influence their decisions. Females have significantly higher frequency of “likes,” comments and messages on Facebook than males do. Based on our observation, the gender difference of social support in sociology is reconfirmed and a pattern behind user behaviour on a social network website is revealed. The results verified that women have higher participation rates, higher frequency of posting and commenting to their friends. In addition, individuals with strong ties have a significantly higher frequency of clicking “like” and posting comments and messages on Facebook than individuals with weak ties do (Luarn et al., 2015).

Conclusion

The Internet and social media are a big factor in the remarkable changes in language. Social media is responsible for the new linguistic revolution that has happened and continues to happen to language. Written language within the context of the Internet has grown more expressive. These expressions came about because people have created a set of rules for conveying information such as intonation and pronunciations of words and phrases. As a result, this has transformed the Internet language into a different form from spoken and written as it shares commonalities and yet had unique features. The discussion of the present paper has highlighted the changes in the vocabulary that came with the need to rename certain elements that are new as a result of the internet or social media such as *wall* or *follower and friend*. Some of these changes in the language represent some of the biggest changes in language caused by semantic changes in which new meanings may be similar to their original meanings. Transformations in language or vocabulary are rising and constant especially in regards to trends. This makes keeping up with new meanings, connotations very difficult as these changes occur over time. The result of these changes is that one word may mean something at a certain time but quickly changes in meaning in a very short time of a month or a year.

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